

Assessing Groundwater Potential Using Aquifer Transmissivity: A Case Study of the Odudunka Erosion Site, Nanka Gully, Anambra State, Nigeria

Nwabinele Emmanuel Onochie, PhD ✉
Department of Ceramic and Technology,
Akanu Ibiam Federal Polytechnic, Unwana, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study area is situated within Nigeria's humid tropical rainforest zone, specifically on a cuesta landscape in the Awka-Orlu uplands, underlain by the Nanka Formation (Early Eocene) and the Imo Shale Formation (Palaeocene). The geological, hydrogeological, geotechnical, and hydrogeochemical characteristics of the region—combined with human activities—have significantly contributed to the initiation and expansion of gully erosion. Numerous springs, streams, and lakes have been observed to drain the gully floodplains. The research revealed that an increase in hydraulic head during the rainy season accelerates subsurface flow, thereby enhancing gully processes. Exposed lithologies were found to host perched aquifers and fully saturated zones, especially within the Nanka Formation, which are susceptible to erosion, landslides, and flooding. This paper evaluates the groundwater potential of selected gully sites within the Nanka region of Anambra State, Nigeria.

Keywords: *Anambra River Basin, Nanka Sands, Groundwater, Gully erosion, Lithology, Aquifer Parameters.*

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Introduction

The Nanka gully erosion site is located within the Anambra Basin, which spans approximately 30,000 square kilometres, extending southward from the confluence of the Niger and Benue rivers. The groundwater potential of southeastern Nigeria, particularly within the Anambra Basin, has been previously assessed using borehole and surface water data by various researchers (Kogbe, 1976).

Gully erosion in Nanka reportedly began around 1850, with an estimated annual growth rate ranging between 20 and 50 metres (Reyment, 1964). The area is characterised by complex,

dynamic multi-aquifer systems, comprising aquifers, aquicludes, aquifuges, and aquitards. Heavy rainfall events result in rising water tables due to capillary action, adhesion, and advective processes. Stratigraphically, the region is composed of loosely consolidated sands and gravels with occasional clay interbeds at the surface. The subsurface is dominated by the Imo Shale Formation, which serves as a confining layer for the aquifers. This geological formation is prominently exposed in the floodplain area of Eziokor Beach, where unregulated sand mining is frequently carried out.

Location of the Study Area

Nanka is located in the Orumba North Local Government Area of Anambra State, Nigeria. The geographic coordinates are approximately 6°03'00"N latitude and 7°05'00"E longitude. It is bordered by several towns, including Oko, Agulu, Ekwulobia, Aguluzigbo, Isuofia, Umuofa, and Awgbu.

Figure 1. Anambra Basin
Source: Egboka 1984.

Geological Setting of the Study Area

The dominant geological unit in the study area is the Nanka Sand Formation, which conformably overlies the Imo Shale of Palaeocene age and is in turn overlain by the Ogwashi-Asaba Formation. The Anambra Basin delineates the southern margin of the Benue Trough and was formed during the Santonian tectonic events, in association with the Afikpo Syncline and the Abakaliki Anticlinorium (Short and Stauble, 1967). The stratigraphic sequence of the basin in this region is presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Sedimentary basins in Nigeria

The area falls within the humid tropical rainforest belt of Nigeria and receives an average annual rainfall of approximately 1800 mm. The Nanka sands are characteristically poorly sorted, sub-rounded to rounded, medium to coarse-grained, and often pebbly.

Methodology

Field investigations were carried out at various gully sites and surrounding areas. The study focused on locations where deeply incised gullies exposed spring water emerging from the multi-aquifer Nanka Formation, as well as areas where drainage-induced floodwaters formed artificial lakes, ponds, and surface water bodies. Interviews were conducted with local residents to gather data on the history and seasonal behaviour of these water bodies.

To assess the groundwater potential of the gully sites, potential aquifers were identified and their hydrogeological properties—such as hydrologic behaviour, seepage characteristics, aquifer thickness, and boundary conditions—were evaluated. Rock and sand samples were collected from multiple locations within the study area. These were subjected to mathematical analyses to derive hydrogeological parameters and stratigraphic logs of exposed aquifer systems at the gully bases. The resulting data provided insight into the lithology, aquifer thickness, and boundaries within the geological formations.

Results and Discussion

Geological and Hydrogeological Characteristics

The local geology of the Eocene-aged Nanka Sandstone reveals that it is composed of loose, friable, and unconsolidated sands, interbedded with thin shale layers. These sands are highly porous and permeable, while the shales serve as aquitards that confine underlying aquifers. During the rainy season, heavy precipitation causes the water table to rise, resulting in increased groundwater flow rates. Conversely, in the dry season, the water table declines due to hydraulic head recession, expanding the unsaturated zone and reducing erosion and gully activity. The water table varies spatially across

the study area (Egboka, 1984). In areas where the overlying lateritic soils have been eroded, groundwater may emerge as seepages, springs, or streams (Egboka, 1985).

Despite the thick unsaturated zone, a substantial rise in the water table occurs during the rainy season due to the high vertical hydraulic conductivity of the overlying medium- to coarse-grained sandy soils, which facilitates rapid recharge of the multi-aquifer system.

Table 1. Aquifer Potential Estimate of Nanka Gully Sites

T(m ² /day)	Aquifer Potential	Location and Value
Over 500	High	Nanka main town: T = 700.84m ² /day
50-500	Moderate	Nanka Erosion site: T = 106.08m ² /day
5-50	Low	
0.5-5	Very low	-
Less than 0.5	Negligible	

Source: Todd, (1980)

Transmissivity Estimates

Transmissivity (T) is defined as the rate at which groundwater of prevailing kinematic viscosity is transmitted through a unit width of aquifer under a unit hydraulic gradient. It is calculated using the formula:

$$T = K \times b \quad (1)$$

Where:

- T = Transmissivity (m²/day)
- K = Hydraulic conductivity (m/day)
- b = Saturated thickness of the aquifer (m)

Alternatively, based on Cooper-Jacob's approximation:

$$T = (2.3 \times Q) / (4\pi \times \Delta S) \quad (2)$$

Sample Calculations

1. Location X₁ – Odudunka, Nanka

- $Q = 918.4 \text{ m}^3/\text{day}$
- $\Delta S = 0.25 \text{ m}$
- $T = (2.3 \times 918.4) / (4 \times 3.1416 \times 0.25)$
= 700.84 m²/day

2. Location X₂ – Erosion Site, Nanka

- $Q = 472.32 \text{ m}^3/\text{day}$
- $\Delta S = 1.0 \text{ m}$
- $T = (2.3 \times 472.32) / (4 \times 3.1416 \times 1.0)$
= 86.75 m²/day

3. Location X_a – Nanka Main Town

- $Q = 472.32 \text{ m}^3/\text{day}$
- $\Delta S = 0.8 \text{ m}$
- $T = (2.3 \times 472.32) / (4 \times 3.1416 \times 0.8)$
= 106.08 m²/day

These results indicate a moderate to high groundwater potential within the study area based on the calculated transmissivity values (see Table 1).

Conclusions

The Nanka Formation consists of loosely consolidated sands and gravels with interbedded shales. The sands are medium to coarse-grained, poorly sorted, and sub-angular to rounded.

Aquifer discharge rates range from 472.32 m³/day to 918.4 m³/day, while transmissivity values vary from 86.75 to 700.84 m²/day, indicating moderate to high aquifer productivity.

The study area possesses significant groundwater potential, as demonstrated by transmissivity values. However, further investigations using additional hydrogeological parameters would help improve groundwater resource development and management in the region.

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